

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS I-IV

Sl. no.	R'	R	Compd. I		Compd. II		Compd. III		Compd. IV	
			M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2'-furyl	H	50 ^a	60	—	60 [*]	134 ^b	50	126 ^b	90
2.	"	2-Cl	65 ^a	90	65 ^b	50	169 ^f	40	102 ^b	70
3.	"	3-OH ₂	43 ^a	70	vis-liq.	35 [*]	126 ^d	25	125 ^d	40
4.	"	4-Cl	87 ^b	90	93 ^b	70 [*]	159 ^d	53	110 ^d	50
5.	"	4-OH ₂	65 ^b	70	73 ^b	65 [*]	120 ^g	80	130 ^b	68
6.	"	2,4-diOl	85 ^a	90	115 ^b	70 [*]	170 ^b	45	134 ^f	50
7.	"	3,4-diCH ₂	58 ^b	77	114 ^b	56 [*]	100 ^d	80	125 ^b	40
8.	"	4-Br	98 ^a	88	90 ^d	70 [*]	160 ^b	65	140 ^b	60
9.	"	2,4-diBr	96 ^a	73	105 ^b	80	170 ^b	40	120 ^b	44
10.	"	2-OH ₂ ,4-Cl	85 ^a	90	140 ^b	60	145 ^b	56	155 ^b	64
11.	"	3-OH ₂ ,4-Cl	69 ^c	92	100 ^b	83	145 ^b	68	124 ^b	97
12.	2'-thienyl	H	59 ^a	50	vis-liq.	30	147 ^b	50	110 ^e	75
13.	"	4-Cl	87 ^b	75	80 ^b	66	125 ^h	58	142 ^b	74
14.	"	4-OH ₂	92 ^c	90	125 ^e	82	119 ^g	66	125 ^e	63
15.	"	3-CH ₂	86 ^a	70	84 ^e	48	160 ^b	50	107 ^e	60
16.	"	3,4-diOH ₂	62 ^a	50	95 ^e	66	117 ^d	50	108 ^b	72
17.	"	2,4-diOl	80 ^a	55	98 ^e	73	169 ^h	63	130 ^b	60
18.	"	2,4-diCH ₂	61 ^a	65	84 ^b	66	146 ^g	60	136 ^b	90
19.	"	2-CH ₂ ,4-Cl	88 ^a	72	56 ^b	66	160 ^d	63	121 ^e	50
20.	"	4-Br	84 ^a	66	58 ^b	66	100 ^e	64	140 ^b	72

Compd. crystallised from : a=Petroleum ether, b=Aq. EtOH, c=MeOH, d=Aq. AcOH, e=Aq. MeOH, f=Benzene, g=Ligroin, h=Toluene + petroleum ether.

*Reported in the literature.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS V

R' = 2'-furyl (compds. Sl. no. 1-11) ;
2'-thienyl (compds. Sl. no. 12-20)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Activity against <i>H. appatermas</i> Zone of inhibition mm
1.	H	(Thick liquid)	23	—
2.	7-Cl	107 ^a	20	13
3.	6-OH ₂	96 ^a	40	—
4.	5-Cl	104 ^a	29	9
5.	5-OH ₂	60 ^a	66	26
6.	5,7-diOl	150 ^a	29	0
7.	5,6-diCH ₂	115 ^a	32	18
8.	5-Br	117 ^b	24	12
9.	5,7-diBr	149 ^c	11	—
10.	5-Cl, 7-CH ₂	109 ^a	33	11
11.	5-Cl, 6-CH ₂	135 ^a	33	—
12.	H	75 ^a	20	—
13.	5-Cl	104 ^d	25	48
14.	5-OH ₂	50 ^e	20	57
15.	6-OH ₂	—	20	—
16.	5,6-diOH ₂	104 ^f	20	39
17.	5,7-diOl	105 ^a	20	0
18.	5,7-diCH ₂	108 ^a	20	31
19.	5-Cl, 7-CH ₂	100 ^a	45	16
20.	5-Br	89 ^a	15	20

Compds. crystallised from : a=Aq. EtOH, b=MeOH + AcOH, c=EtOH + AcOH, d=MeOH, e=petroleum ether, f=benzene + petroleum ether.

References

1. T. SASKAI and T. YOSHIOKA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 42, 826.
2. H. NISHIMURA, M. SHIMIZU, H. UNO, T. HIROOKA, Y. MASUDA and M. KUROKAWA, *Jap. Pat.* 74116056, 74116057 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 83, 10038, 10039).
3. B. M. BHAWAL, G. V. UMALKAR, D. S. MUKADAM and K. A. THAKAR, *Marathwada University J. Sci., Nat. Sci.*, 1977, 16, 7 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 89, 100772).
4. A. J. C. VAN DER STELT, A. J. ZWART VOORSPUIJ and W. THN. NAUTA, *Arsneim.-Forsch.*, 1954, 4, 544 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, 49, 10887).
5. G. V. UMALKAR, B. M. BHAWAL, S. S. BEGUM and K. A. THAKAR, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1977, 15, 406.
6. P. N. WADODKAR and M. G. MARATHE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 145.
7. A. H. BLATT and L. A. RUSSELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1903.
8. K. A. THAKAR, D. D. GOSWAMI and B. M. BHAWAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 1058.
9. H. H. THORNBERRY, *Phytopathology*, 1950, 40, 419.

Synthesis of Possible Antiprotozoal Agents

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BASED on the amebicidal property of emetine several hypothetically modified structural products were synthesised and tested for their antiamebic activity¹⁻⁵. A number of compounds of the types I and II were prepared⁷ and in both these types, the compounds (R=n-hexyl) were appreciably active *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*⁶. A number of

1-(N-Acetylamino)-5-n-butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=COCH₃): It was prepared by the interaction of acetyl chloride with amine and crystallised from dil alcohol (84%), m.p. 135°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1650 cm⁻¹ (amide CO).

The following amides were prepared (R₂, % yield, m.p. in the order shown) : COC₈H₅, 71, 125°; COC₈H₇, 70, 110°. The analytical results for these compounds were in good agreement with the calculated values.

1-(5-n-Butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthylethylamine (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=C₂H₅): The acetylamino compound (IV : n=3, R₁=H, R₂=COCH₃; 2 g) was reduced with LAH (0.2 g) in dry ether (150 ml) in the usual way to yield the product (1.6 g), b.p. 180°/1.5 mm; ν_{max} (film) 3300 cm⁻¹; picrate (EtOH) m.p. 173°. The following amines (IV) were prepared (R₂, % yield, b.p., m.p. of the picrate in the order shown) : C₂H₅, 76, 165°/0.6 mm, 168°; C₄H₉, 83, 178°/1 mm, 162°. The analytical results for these compounds were in good agreement with the calculated values.

1-(5-n-Butyl-7,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthyl)dimethylamine (IV : n=3; R₁=R₂=CH₃): The amine (IV : n=3, R₁=R₂=H; 1.6 g), formic acid (90%, 1.6 g) and formaldehyde (37%, 1.5 ml) were reacted together in the usual way to yield the amine (1.2 g, 68%), b.p. 170°/1.5 mm. The hydrochloride was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture, m.p. 110°.

The following amines (IV : n=3, R₁=CH₃, R₂) were prepared similarly (R₂, % yield, b.p., m.p. of the hydrochloride in the order shown) : C₂H₅, 66, 240°/1.5 mm, 115° (benzene-petroleum ether); C₃H₇, 65, 185°/0.6 mm, 118° (benzene-petroleum ether); C₄H₉, 62, 135°/0.4 mm, 121° (benzene-petroleum ether).

Pharmacology: *In vitro* amebicidal activity of IV against *E. histolytica* was carried out at Kalyani University, West Bengal. Minimum inhibitory concentration (μg/ml) of the following compounds (IV) are (n, R₁, R₂, M.I.C. in the order shown) : 3, H, H, 15.8; 3, CH₃, CH₃, 62.5; 3, CH₃, C₂H₅, nil; 3, CH₃, C₂H₇, nil; 3, CH₃, C₄H₉, nil; 4, H, H, 62.5¹¹; 4, CH₃, CH₃, 250.0, while M.I.C. of emetine hydrochloride is 7.87 μg/ml.

From the screening report it appears that the seven membered compounds are less active than the six membered compounds.

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References

1. R. CHILD and F. L. PYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 2010.

2. F. L. PYMAN, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1937, 56, 789.
3. L. G. GOODWIN, C. A. HOARE and T. M. SHARP, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, 3, 44, 63.
4. J. M. OSBOND, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3464; 1952, 4785.
5. D. HALL MURIEL, S. MAHBOOB and E. E. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1842; 1952, 149.
6. S. MAHBOOB and M. L. DEAR, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. Sect. B*, 1955, 14, 1.
7. C. N. KACHRU and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 611, 768.
8. B. S. KAUSHIVA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. Sect. C*, 1957, 16, 224.
9. H. N. SHARMA and C. N. KACHRU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 371.
10. Personal communication.
11. S. DUTTA, A. PAL, B. P. DRY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 59, 902.
12. H. N. SHARMA and C. N. KACHRU, *Ourr. Sci.*, 1959, 8, 327.

Studies on Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents: Preparation of 1-(4-Amino benzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine and 1-[4-(phenylthioureido)benzoyl]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazine

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LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies have been carried out on antitubercular and antibacterial activity of hydrazone and thiourea. Hydrazones have also been found to possess antibacterial^{1,2}, antifungal³ and insecticidal^{4,5} activities. A number of hydrazones have been synthesised through condensation of acid hydrazide with aldehyde and ketone.

The thioureas with various structural modifications are tuberculostatic^{6,7}, anthelmintics⁸, antifungal⁹ and rodenticides¹⁰. We have prepared 1-[4-(phenylthioureido)benzoyl]-2-substituted-benzalhydrazine from various 1-(4-aminobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine by condensation with phenylisothiocyanate and tested against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

The synthetic sequence of the title compounds is obtained in Scheme 1.

Experimental

4-Aminobenzhydrazide: It was prepared by the reported method¹¹.

1-(4-Aminobenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (II): To the solution of 4-aminobenzhydrazide (0.01 M) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml) added benzaldehyde (0.01 M) in ethanol (95%, 15 ml), content kept for 24 h at room temperature, cooled, filtered, dried and crystallised